

Studies on Inorganic Exchanger : Phosphoantimonic Acid

A. DASH*, K. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN and T. S. MURTHY

Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay-400 085

Manuscript received 6 May 1992, accepted 25 May 1992

The inorganic exchanger phosphoantimonic acid has been prepared and its characteristics evaluated. A method has been developed for the separation of ^{103}Ru and ^{141}Ce from irradiated uranium using phosphoantimonic acid.

In recent times inorganic exchangers are being increasingly used in various separation schemes¹. They are found to possess excellent ion-exchange characteristics and high selectivities in some cases. Along with their reported high chemical and radiation stabilities², these compounds have been found to be very useful in various radioisotope separations. As part of fission product programme, we have studied extensively a number of inorganic exchangers comprising hydrous oxides, heteropoly acid salts and insoluble salts of polyvalent metals like zirconium, titanium, antimony and tin³. Very little work has been reported on phosphoantimonic acid which has been studied to some extent by Ito and Abe⁴. The details of the studies carried out on this compound and its application in the separation of ^{103}Ru and ^{141}Ce from irradiated uranium are given in the present communication. It may be worthwhile to mention that ^{103}Ru is extensively used for various applications like tumor scanning, in the investigation of biochemistry of metallocenes and in biological research for animal pathology⁵. ^{141}Ce finds application in the studies of blood-flow in animals, scinti-scanning, as a tracer in metallurgical industries and studies of honey storage by bees⁶.

Results and Discussion

A number of batches of PPA were prepared. The products obtained in each case were white, hard, transparent, shining granules, stable even in concentrated nitric acid.

As seen from the results (Fig. 1), the distribution ratios for ^{137}Cs at a fixed acid concentration of 0.5 M, increase with equilibrium time from 15 to 90 min and thereafter remain fairly constant. Hence in subsequent experiments a time of 2 h was fixed for equilibration.

The Na^+ capacity was found to be of the order of 2.7 meq/g for all the products. The Sb/P ratio in the various batches of PPA was about 2 : 1. The free moisture content of the product was about 13% in different samples.

The pH-titration curve of the exchanger is shown in Fig. 2. Since only one inflection point is observed in the curve, it appears that the exchanger behaves as monofunctional strong acid

type. From the titration curve it can be concluded that the total capacity is of the order of 3 meq/g of the exchanger and this is comparable to that determined experimentally. The specificity for all cations at low acidity is probably due to the strong acidic nature of the $-\text{OH}$ group.

Fig. 1. Determination of equilibrium time.

Fig. 2. pH-Titration curve for polyphosphoantimonic acid.

Table 1 shows the distribution ratios of various elements at acidities ranging from 0.2 to 10 *M* with respect to nitric acid. From the distribution ratios obtained for the various elements which are likely to be present in irradiated uranium, it is observed that all elements are taken up by PPA at lower acidities. The values show a gradual decrease with increase in acidity. However, ruthenium exhibits very little uptake up to 0.5 *M* and is not taken up at any of the acidities greater than 0.5 *M* by PPA.

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION RATIOS OF VARIOUS ELEMENTS AT DIFFERENT HNO₃ CONCENTRATIONS

Element	HNO ₃ concn. (<i>M</i>)							
	0.2	0.5	1.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
Na	2 653	1 608	800	476	180	99	46	37
K	245	108	48	25	12	6	4	NU
Rb	4 331	2 496	1 012	378	110	29	12	NU
Cs	14 985	3 785	1 501	924	255	60	15	3
Sr	10 535	6 850	5 560	2 050	262	37	3	NU
Ba	5 100	731	116	25	3			←NU→
Y	2 681	2 373	2 169	469	53	16	5	2
La	5 176	3 203	1 982	194	17	3		←NU→
Ce ^{III}	4 263	4 007	338	42				←NU→
Ce ^{IV}	6 680	1 279	139	17				←NU→
Nd	6 916	3 552	930	94	10			←NU→
Sm	12 600	6 897	557	52	5			←NU→
Eu	2 569	6 870	7 255	989	763	18	8	5
Zr	1 412	338	1 324	803	761	242	239	188
Nb	118	944	1 143	1 045	761	581	335	215
Ru	50	28						←NU→
UO ₂ ^{II}	18 530	5 220	1 490	390	137	113	60	43

NU=No uptake.

The pattern of behaviour of the various elements with respect to PPA showed that ruthenium is not

taken up at any of the acidities greater than 1 *M*. This indicates a possibility that ruthenium can be effectively separated from all other elements if the feed solution at acidities greater than 1 *M* is passed through a column of PPA. This assumption was verified by passing a solution similar to the one obtained after dissolution of uranium spiked with tracers of ⁹⁵Zr—⁹⁵Nb, ¹⁴¹Ce, ¹⁴⁰Ba—¹⁴⁰La, ¹⁰³Ru, ⁸⁹Sr, ⁹¹Y, through a column of PPA. The effluent from the absorption step was collected and analysed using a multichannel analyser. The spectrum indicates the peaks characteristics of ¹⁰³Ru only.

From the distribution ratios obtained (Table 1) it was observed that PPA takes up cerium at acidities up to 1 *M* with high distribution ratios. The values decrease beyond 1 *M* and there is no uptake for cerium at acidities greater than 6 *M*. In a sequential scheme, after the preliminary separation of ⁹⁵Zr—⁹⁵Nb, ¹⁴⁰Ba, it could be envisaged that ¹⁰³Ru and ¹⁴¹Ce could be mutually separated by passing through PPA column and eluting ¹⁴¹Ce with higher molarities of nitric acid. This was confirmed by carrying out the experiment. The spectrum of the effluent and washing were checked with a 4 K analyser. This clearly indicates characteristic peak of ¹⁰³Ru free from ¹⁴¹Ce (Fig. 3).

The absorbed ¹⁴¹Ce was eluted with nitric acid of molarities ranging from 4 to 12 *M* HNO₃ and from the results it was observed that ¹⁴¹Ce could be eluted with 8 *M* HNO₃ and an overall yield of 80% was obtained in about twenty column volumes. The elution curve obtained has a sharp maximum

Fig. 3. Spectrum of effluent.

with comparatively less trailing (Fig. 4). The purity of the elute ^{141}Ce was evaluated using 4 K multi-channel analyser and the product was found to be

Fig. 4. Elution curves of ^{141}Ce from PPA; Conc. of HNO_3 : (1) 12, (2) 10, (3) 8, (4) 6 and (5) 4 M.

extremely pure showing only peaks pertaining to ^{141}Ce (Fig. 5).

Chemical process for ^{103}Ru recovery: The modified procedure for the recovery of ^{103}Ru from irradiated uranium is as follows (Fig. 6). Irradiated uranium was dissolved in concentrated HNO_3 and evaporated to near dryness. The residue was taken up after cooling in 6 M HNO_3 and passed through a column of silica gel conditioned with 6 M HNO_3 to separate ^{95}Zr — ^{95}Nb . The column was profusely washed with 10 column volumes of 6 M HNO_3 . The effluent and washing from the silica gel was evaporated to near dryness. The residue was dissolved in 0.2 M HNO_3 and passed through a column of hydrous manganese dioxide conditioned with 0.2 M HNO_3 wherein ^{140}Ba , ^{141}Ce and ^{103}Ru were held up. The column was then washed with water and ^{140}Ba eluted with 2 M HNO_3 .

Cerium and ruthenium were eluted with 10 M HNO_3 and the eluent acidities adjusted to 1 M with respect to HNO_3 and was loaded on a PPA column preconditioned appropriately. The column was washed with 10 column volumes of 1 M HNO_3 . ^{103}Ru gets separated at this stage in the effluent.

Conclusion: The inorganic exchanger phospho-antimonic acid has been studied for its ion-exchange characteristics and properties with a view to its possible use in radioisotope separation. From the experimental data obtained the separation of ^{103}Ru of high radioactive purity from irradiated uranium has been achieved. It has also been possible to effect a mutual separation of ^{141}Ce and ^{103}Ru on a PPA column and recover the ^{141}Ce subsequently.

Fig. 5. Spectrum of eluent.

A number of batches were processed using the revised method which is now being currently used for regular large scale production of this isotope.

Experimental

All reagents used were of E. Merck or B.D.H. (AnalaR) grade.

All radioactive tracers used ^{137}Cs , $^{85+87}\text{Sr}$, ^{95}Zr – ^{95}Nb , ^{91}Y , ^{141}Ce were available from the Isotope Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre.

Preparation of the exchanger : To 0.1 M phosphoric acid (2000 ml), antimony pentachloride (50 ml) was added with vigorous stirring. The precipitate was allowed to stand overnight, then washed with distilled water till the pH of the wash-water was 1, and air-dried at room temperature for 3 days and subsequently in an air-oven at 40–50° for 2 days. The gel thus obtained broke down easily in to small particles with cracking sound when it was immersed in 2 M HNO_3 . The product was again washed with water to make it free of adhering materials, air-dried and stored.

Variation of distribution ratios with equilibration time : Samples (0.2 g) of the exchangers were weighed separately ; 0.5 M HNO_3 (1.0 ml) containing 50000 CPM/ml of ^{137}Cs was added to each sample and then equilibrated for different time intervals.

Evaluation of distribution ratios : The exchanger (0.2 g) was equilibrated with HNO_3 (20 ml) of respective molarities containing 1 μCi of tracer. The time of equilibration was 2 h and wrist-arm mechanical shaker was used to ensure good mixing. After equilibration the solid was allowed to settle and

then filtered off. 1.0 ml of the filtrate was counted in a well type scintillation counter and compared with the reference.

The distribution ratios were calculated using the relationship,

$$K_d = \frac{\text{Amount of the element taken up CPM/g of exchanger}}{\text{Amount of the element CPM present per ml of the solution at equilibrium}}$$

The distribution ratios of the various elements at all acidities ranging from 0.2 to 10 M with respect to nitric acid were determined. The results are given in Table 1.

Determination of exchange capacity : The exchanger (1 g) taken in a glass column (12 cm \times 6 mm dia) was washed with 20-column volumes of distilled water to remove free acid present in it. The washing was continued till the effluent of the column attained neutral pH. Sodium chloride solution (0.1 M ; 200 ml) was passed through the column at a very slow flow rate of 0.1 ml min^{-1} . The effluent from the column was collected and titrated against 0.1 M NaOH.

Estimation of antimony to phosphorous ratio : The exchanger (1 g) was mixed with fusion mixture (1 : 1 $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3 + \text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$; 6 g) and fused in a platinum dish using an oxyburshane flame. The fused mass was cooled and dissolved in 6 M HCl (250 ml). Phosphorous and antimony were estimated using standard chemical method⁷.

Determination of free water content : The exchanger (1 g) was heated at 100° till constant weight was

Fig. 6. Separation of Ru-103 and Ce-141 from irradiated uranium.

obtained and percentage moisture was calculated from the loss in weight.

pH-titration curve: To the exchanger (0.5 g) taken separately, 0.2 M NaCl solution (20 ml) was added to each of them and kept for 4 h with occasional stirring. To each sample varying amounts of 0.1 M NaOH were added to adjust the pH and kept at room temperature with intermittent shaking till equilibrium was attained. The pH of the equilibrated solution was then measured by means of a pH meter. The pH of the solution was plotted against number of milliequivalents of NaOH added per g of the exchanger. The pH-titration curve obtained is given in Fig. 1.

Column experiments: The column had the following characteristics: dimension, 20 cm × 1.15 cm dia; bed dimension, 5 cm × 1.15 cm dia; column volume, 5.5 ml; flow rate, 0.1 ml min⁻¹. PPA (6 g) in 1 M HNO₃ was transferred to a glass column provided with glass wool padding at the bottom. The column was then washed with 10-column volumes of 1 M HNO₃. Stock solutions similar to one obtained after dissolution of irradiated uranium spiked with ⁹⁵Zr-⁹⁵Nb, ¹⁰³Ru, ¹⁴¹Ce, ¹⁴⁰Ba-¹⁴⁰La, ⁸⁹Sr, ⁹¹Y, corresponding to an activity of 1.0 ml=10000 CPM, were prepared. This feed solution was percolated through the exchanger bed by gravity and the effluent collected continuously. The spectrum of the effluent was taken and analysed using a multichannel analyser.

Separation of ¹⁴¹Ce and ¹⁰³Ru on a PPA column: PPA (6 g) in 1 M HNO₃ was transferred to a glass column provided with a glass wool padding at the bottom. After washing the column with double-distilled water (50 ml) it was conditioned with 10-column volumes of 1 M HNO₃. 50 ml of the solution at 1 M with respect to HNO₃ containing tracers of ¹⁰³Ru and ¹⁴¹Ce (40000 CPM) was passed through the column and washed with 1 M HNO₃ (100 ml) till the washings showed no activity.

Elution studies of ¹⁴¹Ce from PPA column: The exchanger PPA (6 g) was loaded in a suitable column with a glass wool padding at the bottom. This was conditioned with 10-column volumes of HNO₃. The column volume in this case was 5.5 ml. 20 ml of

1 M HNO₃ containing ¹⁴¹Ce (20000 CPM/ml) was passed through the exchanger till breakthrough was attained. The column was washed with 1 M HNO₃ and washing collected till free from activity. The absorbed ¹⁴¹Ce was eluted with HNO₃ of different molarities. 5 ml fractions were collected and counted in a well type scintillation counter, NaI(Tl) type.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Mr. A. C. Eapen, Head, Isotope Division, for his keen interest in the work.

References

1. A. CLEARFIELD, "Inorganic Ion Exchange Materials", CRC Press, Boca Raton, Florida, 1982; J. A. MARINSKY and Y. MARCUS, "Ion Exchange and Solvent Extraction", Marcel Decker, New York, 1973, Vols. 4 and 5; J. INIEDY, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, 1, 157; M. J. FULLER, *Chromatogr. Rev.*, 1971, 45, 14; V. VESELEY and V. PEKAREK, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 219; A. BRANDONE, S. MELONI, F. GIRARDI and E. SABBIONI, *Analisis*, 1972, 2, 200.
2. C. B. AMPHLETT, "Proceedings: Conference on Peaceful Uses of Atomic Energy", Geneva, 1958, 28, 17; B. T. KENNA, SAND-80-1212, National Laboratories, Livermore, 1981; G. PFEPPER, H. MAI, M. HERMANN and H. LANGGUTH, *Radiochim. Acta*, 1981, 28, 177; I. YASUSHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1963, 36, 1316; V. V. GRAMOV and V. I. SPICIN, *Atomn. Energ. (USSR)*, 1963, 14, 491.
3. T. S. MURTHY, K. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN, M. ANANTHAKRISHNAN, K. S. RAMANI and R. N. VARMA, BARC-894, 1976; T. S. MURTHY, K. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN, M. ANANTHAKRISHNAN, K. S. RAMANI, R. N. VARMA and M. C. ANTHONY, BARC-893, 1977; T. S. MURTHY, K. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN, M. ANANTHAKRISHNAN, K. S. RAMANI and R. N. VARMA, BARC-895, 1976; T. S. MURTHY "Proceedings of DAE Nuclear Chemistry and Radiochemistry Symposium", Waltair, 1980.
4. T. ITO and M. ABE, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1961, 34, 1736.
5. M. V. GANDER and P. J. K. MORGAN, *Oikos*, 1981, 36, 207; D. DEAST and L. G. WALCH, *Int. J. Appl. Radn. Isotope*, 1979, 30, 463; K. MIZUKAWA, *Okayama Igakkai Zasshi*, 1979, 91, 135.
6. J. MAYER, *Radioisotopy*, 1982, 23, 647; D. I. ALINDZHANOVA, *Uzb. Khim. Zh.*, 1977, 1, 18; P. DONALD, *Apidologie*, 1974, 5, 109.
7. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., ELBS, London, 1981, pp. 366, 402.